

A thermodynamically consistent phase field model for mixed-mode fracture in rock-like materials

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Abstract

A thermodynamically consistent phase field model with new crack driving forces is proposed to simulate the mixed-mode fracture phenomena in rock-like materials. The governing equations are derived using the volumetric and deviatoric strain split. Based on the Benzeggagh–Kenane failure criterion, our model captures the salient features of different fracture modes, e.g., pure tensile dominated fracture, pure shear dominated fracture, and mixed tensile-shear fracture and mixed compressive-shear fracture phenomena. The fully monolithic algorithm enables our new phase field model to obtain stable numerical results with fast numerical convergence. The three-point bending test of concrete beam is considered for validation. The numerical results are collaborated by test results from the literature. Afterwards, the numerical model is applied to study crack propagation and coalescence in rock-like specimens under uniaxial compression.

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1. Introduction

Fractures are ubiquitous in geological materials under tectonic stresses, which can be explained in principle by linear elastic fracture mechanics particularly by Griffith's theory [1]. For quantitative description of fracture process, however, numerical methods have become indispensable for modeling the propagation and coalescence of fractures in rock/rock-like materials [2–9]. The relevant research plays an important role in a number of science and engineering disciplines, e.g. earth science, geology, civil and petroleum engineering.

During the past decades, many numerical methods for fracturing processes were developed, which can be mainly categorized into line crack models [2,10,11] and smeared crack models [12–14]. In the line crack models, cracks are represented by introducing new boundaries, which possess exactly the geometric topology. In this way, paths of discontinuities can be tracked. In order to satisfy the discontinuity of displacement fields across crack surfaces, some specific techniques for introducing the discontinuous fields are implemented into the line crack models. Several line crack models including Strong Discontinuous Method, Generalized/eXtended Finite Element Method, Cohesive Zone Models, have been developed to simulate crack growth paths by using numerical interpolations

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of displacement jumps [2,10,15], the enriched discontinuous basis functions [16,17], interfacial elements [18], respectively. The aforementioned line crack models were successfully applied to crack propagation and coalescence of geomaterials [19–22].

In contrast to line crack models, the smeared crack models make use of the diffuse crack topology, which originated from the continuum damage mechanics (CDM), via smoothed transition regions between intact and fully damaged material states [23–26]. The smeared cracks are simulated by introducing the continuum damage variables, which are used to model the initiation and propagation of cracks. The non-local integral damage model [27,28], strain gradient damage model [29], peridynamic model [30–32], thick level set model [33] and phase field model [24,25,34–36] are the major smeared crack models.

Since the early attempts of a variational model for quasi-static crack evolution by Francfort and Marigo [37], phase field models have attracted much attention. In the past two decades, different phase field models are developed to solve different fracture problems in the scientific and engineering fields, including quasi-static/static fracture problems [38,39], dynamic fracture problems [35,40], ductile fracture problems [41,42], cohesive fracture problems [29,43], hydraulic fracture problems [44–47], multiscale fracture problems [48], and etc. Although the previous phase field models had great success in many fracturing problems, most of them did not distinguish between tensile and shear cracks. Consequently, they cannot be directly employed to model fracturing in rocks.

Tensile cracks, shear cracks and mixed tensile/compressive cracks commonly appear in rock and rock-like materials subjected to compressive loads [49–52]. To account for stress degradations in tension, the spectral decomposition [24,25] and the volumetric–deviatoric split [13] were used to distinguish between the positive and negative components of strain tensors to simulate the brittle fracture phenomena [26,53,54]. However, in rocks and rock-like materials, the compression-induced degradation is also rather common, which cannot be sufficiently modeled using spectral decomposition or volumetric–deviatoric split. Based on the framework of stress decomposition, Zhang et al. [55] proposed a modified phase field model, which can distinguish between wing cracks (i.e., Mode-I fracture) and secondary cracks (i.e., Mode-II fracture) using the critical energy release rates. This model is used to simulate mixed mode crack propagation in rock-like materials. Subsequently, Bryant and Sun [56] proposed a mixed-mode phase field model with consistent kinematics to simulate mixed-mode and secondary cracks. This is achieved by introducing an algorithm to determine the crack propagation direction based on the maximization of energy dissipation. A phase field model containing crack driving forces considering the influence of cohesion and internal friction angle is proposed by Zhou et al. [57] for brittle compressive-shear fracture in rock-like materials, and then it is applied to investigate the double crack propagation [58] and hydraulic fracture [59]. Fei and Choo [60] and You et al. [61] introduced two scalar phase fields in the classical phase field model framework to simulate the tensile cracks and shear cracks, respectively. However, the two scalar variables in these two phase field models lead the mixed tensile/compressive-shear cracks to be regarded as a black-and-white issue. In addition, different failure criteria, such as Mohr–Coulomb criterion [62] and unified tensile fracture criterion [63], were incorporated to phase field models to predict the damage. Based on these failure criteria, the associated phase field models were proposed by deriving the new fracture driving forces for evolution of tensile and shear cracks. Although the existing phase field models have been successful in simulating the mixed-mode fracture in rock and rock-like materials, only tensile-shear part [55] or only compressive-shear part [57,58] is taken into consideration in the fracture driving forces. The fracture driving forces in phase field model, which take both mixed tensile-shear and mixed compressive-shear degradations into considerations, have not been reported yet. Both mixed tensile-shear and mixed compressive-shear damage degradations realistically reproduce the fracture phenomena in rock and rock-like materials under compression.

This study aims at proposing a modified thermodynamically consistent phase field model with new crack driving forces to simulate mixed-mode fracture in rock and rock-like materials under compression. It has two attractive features. First, the new crack driving force related to the history variable (i.e., phase field variable) is decomposed into a positive volumetric part and a deviatoric deformation part. This decomposition is based on energy and thermodynamically conservation principles. These two components of the new crack driving forces are used to distinguish between mode-I and mode-II fractures based on the Benzeggagh–Kenane Semi-empirical failure criterion [64], allowing the model to capture the mixed mode tensile, shear, and compressive fractures in a unified framework. Second, a fully monolithic solution strategy is proposed, which converges faster compared to the common staggered solving scheme in other phase field models. Furthermore, several numerical examples of fissured rock-like specimens under the uniaxial compression are provided to demonstrate its predictive capability

by qualitatively and quantitatively comparing with the existing laboratory experimental results. The mechanism of mixed-mode fractures in rock-like materials under the uniaxial compression is also investigated by simulations.

This paper is organized as follows: the formulations of the thermodynamically consistent phase field model for mixed-mode fracture are derived in Section 2. In Section 3, the numerical implementation of this model is introduced. In Section 4, two benchmark examples are simulated for validation. Furthermore, the mechanism of compressive fracturing in the fissured rock-like materials is investigated in Section 5. Finally, conclusions and perspectives are drawn in Section 6.

2. Thermodynamically consistent phase field model

2.1. Regularization of crack topology

A brittle elastic body occupying a computational domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^\delta$, where $\delta = 1, 2, 3$, is bounded by the Dirichlet boundary $\partial\Omega_u$ and the Neumann boundary $\partial\Omega_t$, as shown in Fig. 1. The two boundaries have the following relationships: (i) $\partial\Omega = \partial\Omega_t \cup \partial\Omega_u$; and (ii) $\partial\Omega_t \cap \partial\Omega_u = \emptyset$. In the phase field model, the strong discontinuity Γ in the computational domain Ω is described by an auxiliary phase field variable $d(\mathbf{x}) \subseteq \Omega \times \Gamma \mapsto [0, 1]$. It can be observed from Fig. 1 that $d(r) = 0$ indicates that solid material is intact, while $d(r) = 1$ means that the solid material is fully broken, where r denotes the distance between the material point \mathbf{x} and the sharp crack surface Γ .

Considering the homogenization of micro-cracks and micro-voids, Miehe et al. [24] and Miehe et al. [25] introduced an exponential function, i.e., $d(\mathbf{x}) = \exp\left\{-\frac{r(\mathbf{x})}{\ell_c}\right\}$ to describe the regularized crack topology based on the Γ -convergence theory [65,66]. The characteristic scale parameter ℓ_c represents the width of diffusive crack, as shown in Fig. 1.

To describe the diffusive crack topology in a computational domain, Miehe et al. [24] defined the following formulation of crack.

$$\Gamma_d = \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{1}{2\ell_c} d^2 + \frac{\ell_c}{2} (\nabla d)^2 \right] d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \gamma(d, \nabla d) d\Omega \quad (1)$$

in which $\gamma(d, \nabla d)$ denotes the crack surface density function.

$$\gamma(d, \nabla d) = \frac{1}{2\ell_c} d^2 + \frac{\ell_c}{2} |\nabla d|^2 \quad (2)$$

2.2. Governing equations

In the phase field model [24,37], the total potential energy of the continuum solid body Ω with the discontinuous structure Γ is composed of the stored elastic energy in solid and the surface energy stemming from the initiation and propagation of the discontinuous structure. The corresponding total potential energy function $\Psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ is formulated.

$$\Psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \int_{\Omega \setminus \Gamma} \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \mathcal{G}_c d\Gamma \quad (3)$$

where $\psi_0(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ is the stored elastic energy density, and \mathcal{G}_c represents the critical energy release rate in linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM). The initial stored elastic energy density $\psi_0(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ can be written as

$$\psi_0(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})^2 + \mu \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

where λ and μ are Lamé constants, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T)$ is the strain tensor, where \mathbf{u} denotes the displacement field.

To describe the total potential energy during the evolution of the discontinuous structure Γ_d in the solid Ω , the functional total potential energy reads

$$\Psi_\ell(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) = \int_{\Omega} g(d) \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{G}_c \gamma(d, \nabla d) d\Omega \quad (5)$$

where $g(d)$ is the degradation function to describe the remaining elastic strain energy stored in the solid [24,25,67], which is expressed as

$$g(d) = [(1-d)^2 + k] \quad (6)$$

where k is a positive constant for avoiding numerical instability [25,68].

Fig. 1. The schematic regularization of crack topology in the computational domain Ω within the framework of phase field model.

According to the variational principle for brittle fracture proposed by Francfort and Marigo [37], the Euler–Lagrange free energy functional $\Pi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \Gamma)$ can be approximated as the following form in the phase field model.

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \Gamma) &\simeq \Pi_{\ell_c}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) = \Psi_{\ell_c}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) - W_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{t}, \mathbf{u}) \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \psi_{\ell_c}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{G}_c \gamma(d, \nabla d) d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b}^T \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega_t} \bar{\mathbf{t}}^T \cdot \mathbf{u} dS \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{b} is the body force vector and $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ denotes the prescribed traction vector.

In the original phase field model, Miehe et al. [24,25] decomposed the elastic strain energy into tensile and compressive parts to capture tensile brittle fractures.

$$\psi_{\ell_c}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) = [(1-d)^2 + k] \psi_0^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \psi_0^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \quad (8)$$

where ψ_0^{\pm} are the tensile and compressive parts of stored energy density

With respect to displacement field \mathbf{u} and phase field d , the stationary form of this variational problem for the admissible displacement field and phase field yields

$$\delta \Pi_{\ell}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}), d) = \frac{\partial \Pi_{\ell}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{\partial \Pi_{\ell}}{\partial d} \cdot \delta d = 0 \quad (9)$$

Based on thermodynamics [25], the macroscopic stress–strain relation is derived as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) := \frac{\partial \psi_{\ell}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \underbrace{g(d) \frac{\partial \psi_0^+}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}}_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial \psi_0^-}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}}_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})} \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor.

Therefore, strong forms of the governing equations in the phase field model with the Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions can be summarized as

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) + \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (11a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_t \quad (11b)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_u \quad (11c)$$

$$(1-d) \mathcal{H}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) - \frac{\mathcal{G}_c}{2\ell_c} d + \frac{\ell_c}{2} \mathcal{G}_c \nabla^2 d = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (11d)$$

$$\nabla d \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega \cup \Gamma \quad (11e)$$

where $\mathcal{H}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) = \max\{\psi_0^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})\}$ represents the maximum positive reference energy, which ensures the crack irreversibility [24,25].

2.3. Mixed-mode fracture

2.3.1. Energy and stress decomposition

In contrast to the previous phase field model [24,25], which was employed by Zhang et al. [55] and Bryant and Sun [56] to simulate rock fracture problems, in this study, the strain tensor is decomposed into the volumetric and deviatoric parts.

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{sph}} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} \tag{12}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{sph}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}}$ are the volumetric and deviatoric strain tensors, respectively; and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} = \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \frac{1}{3}\text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})\mathbf{I}$.

Subsequently, the stored energy density function consists of three parts: the pure dilational part ψ_n^+ , the pure compressive part ψ_n^- and the tensile/compressive-shear part ψ_t . In this research, the material degradation stemming from ψ_n^+ and ψ_t is taken into consideration, where damages caused by mixed tensile-shear and compressive-shear deformations are considered

$$\psi_\ell(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = \psi_n^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) + \psi_t(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) + \psi_n^-(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \tag{13}$$

where

$$\psi_n^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = g(d) \frac{K}{2} \text{tr}^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})^2 \tag{14a}$$

$$\psi_t(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = g(d) \mu \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} \tag{14b}$$

$$\psi_n^-(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) = \frac{K}{2} \text{tr}^-(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})^2 \tag{14c}$$

in which K and μ are the bulk and shear moduli of undamaged materials.

In the phase field model with unilateral contact, to prevent the interpenetration of crack surfaces in the compressed region, we introduce the following decomposition of the trace of strain.

$$\text{tr}^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) = \max\{0, \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})\} \tag{15a}$$

$$\text{tr}^-(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) = \min\{0, \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})\} \tag{15b}$$

Based on the volumetric and deviatoric strain split [13], the new Euler–Lagrange free energy functional $\Pi(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \Gamma)$ can be re-approximated as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_\ell(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = & \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} g(d) \left[\frac{K}{2} \text{tr}^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})^2 + \mu \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} \right] d\Omega}_{\int_{\Omega} \psi_n^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) + \psi_t(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) d\Omega} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \frac{K}{2} \text{tr}^-(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})^2 d\Omega}_{\int_{\Omega} \psi_n^-(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) d\Omega} \\ & + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathcal{G}_c \gamma(d, \nabla d) d\Omega}_{\text{Fracture energy dissipation}} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b}^T \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega_t} \bar{\mathbf{t}}^T \cdot \mathbf{u} dS}_{W_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{t}, \mathbf{u})} \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The corresponding stationary form of this variational problem for the admissible displacement field and phase field reads

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi_\ell = & \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b}^T \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega_t} \bar{\mathbf{t}}^T \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} dS}_{= \frac{\partial \Pi_\ell}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}} \\ & + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \mathcal{G}_c \left(\frac{1}{\ell_c} d \delta d + \ell_c \nabla d \cdot \delta \nabla d \right) d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} 2(1-d) (\psi_n^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) + \psi_t(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d)) \delta d d\Omega}_{= \frac{\partial \Pi_\ell}{\partial d} \cdot \delta d} \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Fig. 2. The schematic of mixed-mode fracture in the linear elastic brittle solids.

2.3.2. Thermodynamically mixed-mode crack driving forces

In the new thermodynamically consistent phase field model, the critical fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_c in Griffith theory is decomposed into a mode-I fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_{Ic} and a mode-II fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_{IIc} . The standard Traction–Separation Law (TSL) with sudden stress drop is adopted to capture the brittle fracture behaviors in rock/rock-like materials, as illustrated in Fig. 2. For the simple two-dimensional (2D) cases, the pure normal opening mode (mode-I fracture) is depicted on the plane $0 - t_{eq} - \delta_n$ when $t_{eq} = \sigma$, and the pure tangential sliding mode (mode-II fracture) is plotted on the plane $0 - t_{eq} - \delta_t$ when $t_{eq} = \tau$ [69,70]. It can be observed from Fig. 2 that the mode-I fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_{Ic} and mode-II fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_{IIc} are equal to $k_{n0}\delta_{n0}^2/2$ and $k_{t0}\delta_{t0}^2/2$, respectively. For the mixed mode-II fracture, an equivalent traction $t_{eq} = \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \tau^2}$ and an equivalent displacement $\delta_{eq} = \sqrt{\delta_n^2 + \delta_t^2}$ are introduced [70]. Therefore, on the basis of Benzeggagh–Kenane semi-empirical failure criterion [64], the equivalent mixed mode I–II fracture energy release rate is expressed as

$$\mathcal{G}_c = \mathcal{G}_{Ic} + (\mathcal{G}_{IIc} - \mathcal{G}_{Ic}) \left(\frac{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic} + \mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right)^m = \mathcal{G}_{Ic} + (\mathcal{G}_{IIc} - \mathcal{G}_{Ic}) \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{H}} \right)^m \tag{18}$$

where \mathcal{G}_{Ic} and \mathcal{G}_{IIc} are the critical fracture energy release rates for mode-I and mode-II fracture modes, respectively; m denotes the positive parameter in the semi-empirical fracture criterion that is adopted as $m = 2.6$ in this study.

In Eq. (18), when $\mathcal{H}_t = 0$, the pure mode-I fracture occurs and we have $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_{Ic}$. On the other hand, if $\mathcal{H}_t = \mathcal{H}$, the pure mode-II fracture happens and we have $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_{IIc}$. Meanwhile, Eq. (18) not only can reduce to pure mode-I or pure mode-II fracture energy release rate, but also can describe the equivalent mixed mode I–II fracture energy release rate that related to \mathcal{G}_{Ic} , \mathcal{G}_{IIc} and the current deformation state. This treatment overcomes the simple sum in other phase field models [55]. Thus, crack evolution equation, i.e., Eq. (11d), can be transformed into the following form in the new phase field model.

$$(1 - d) \frac{\mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{G}_c} + \frac{\ell_c}{2} \nabla^2 d - \frac{1}{2\ell_c} d = 0 \tag{19}$$

in which $\frac{\mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{G}_c}$ is the normalized driving force for the crack growth.

In the previous phase field models for mixed-mode fractures [55,56], the modified crack growth driving force $\left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_I}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_{II}}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right)$ is similar to F-criterion [71], i.e., $\mathcal{F} = \frac{\mathcal{G}_I(\theta)}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{G}_{II}(\theta)}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}}$. However, with the criterion, \mathcal{G} -criterion, $\frac{\mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{G}_c} < \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_I}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_{II}}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right)$ may occur, which results in numerical instability in predicting crack growth paths. To solve this

issue, the crack growth driving term in the crack evolution equation, i.e., Eq. (19), is approximated as follows

$$\frac{\mathcal{H}}{\mathcal{G}_c} \simeq \eta \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) \tag{20}$$

where $\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}}$ is the normalized driving force for the purely tensile fractures caused by volumetric dilation, whereas $\frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}}$ is the normalized driving force for the fractures induced by deviatoric deformation, including the mixed tensile-shear fracture, the mixed compressive-shear fractures and the purely shear fractures in solids, and η is the corrected parameter to prevent instabilities. It has the following form

$$\eta = \frac{\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{G}_{Ic}\mathcal{G}_{IIc})}{\mathcal{G}_c(\mathcal{H}_t\mathcal{G}_{Ic} + \mathcal{H}_n\mathcal{G}_{IIc})} \tag{21}$$

in which, \mathcal{H}_n is the history-field value of the stored elastic energy induced by volumetric dilation, and \mathcal{H}_t is the history-field value of the stored elastic energy stemming from deviatoric deformation. These two kinds of crack driving forces are both history-field variable.

To prevent crack healing and ensure the energy conservation, the modified crack evolution equation with the new crack driving forces reaches the following form by substituting Eqs. (20) and (21) into Eq. (19).

$$(1 - d) \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d)}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d)}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) \eta + \frac{\ell_c}{2} \nabla^2 d - \frac{1}{2\ell_c} d = 0 \tag{22}$$

where $\mathcal{H}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) = \mathcal{H}_n(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) + \mathcal{H}_t(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d)$ is a constant value. The original crack evolution equation in the previous phase field models, i.e., Eq. (19), is a special case of the current crack evolution equation Eq. (22) when $\mathcal{G}_{Ic} = \mathcal{G}_{IIc}$.

Thus, in the proposed thermodynamically consistent phase field model, the normalized mixed-mode fracture driving forces read

$$\mathcal{H}_m = \frac{1}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} \mathcal{H}_n + \frac{1}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \mathcal{H}_t \tag{23}$$

Following [55,63], the frictional contact responses are also ignored in the new phase field model. The new crack driving forces composed of volumetric and deviatoric parts can capture the fracture phenomena induced by the volumetric and deviatoric deformations. Compared to the models for tensile shear fractures [55] and the models for compressive-shear fractures [57,58], the proposed new crack driving forces can consider the mixed tensile-shear cracks, mixed compressive-shear cracks, and purely shear cracks in a unified framework. Furthermore, in our proposed model, the different behaviors between mixed tensile-shear and mixed compressive-shear fractures can be considered by altering the ratio of \mathcal{H}_n to \mathcal{H} in Eq. (18).

In the new crack evolution Eq. (22), when the volumetric part of the crack driving force $2\ell_c\mathcal{H}_n$ exceeds the critical fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_{Ic} , mode-I fractures will happen, as shown in Fig. 3(a). When the deviatoric part of the new crack driving force $2\ell_c\mathcal{H}_t$ reaches the critical fracture energy release rate \mathcal{G}_{IIc} with small or null volumetric dilational part, mode-II fractures will occurs, as shown in Fig. 3(b). For the mixed-mode fractures, the volumetric dilation and deviatoric deformation both contribute to the crack driving forces, as shown in Fig. 3(c). When $2\ell_c\mathcal{H}_m = 2\ell_c \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) = 1$ holds, we have mixed mode I–II fractures.

Therefore, the strong form in the proposed thermodynamically consistent phase field model with the new crack driving forces for mixed-mode fractures can be written as follows

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) + \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } \Omega \tag{24a}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{t}} \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_t \tag{24b}$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega_u \tag{24c}$$

$$(1 - d) \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) \eta + \frac{\ell_c}{2} \nabla^2 d - \frac{1}{2\ell_c} d = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \tag{24d}$$

$$\nabla d \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega \cup \Gamma \tag{24e}$$

Fig. 3. The schematic of Mode-I, Mode-II and Mixed-mode I-II crack driving forces in the phase field model.

2.4. Irreversibility

According to the thermodynamically consistent framework, the evolution of the phase field, i.e., crack growth paths in the proposed numerical model should satisfy the following crack irreversibility principle.

$$\Gamma(t) \subseteq \Gamma(t + \Delta t) \tag{25}$$

To conveniently ensure the crack irreversibility, the new volumetric and deviatoric crack driving forces are corrected as follows

$$\mathcal{H}_n(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \{\psi_n^+(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d)\} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{sph}} : \mathbb{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{sph}}, d_c \right\} \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \geq 0 \tag{26a}$$

$$\mathcal{H}_n(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = 0 \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) < 0 \tag{26b}$$

$$\mathcal{H}_t(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d) = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \{\psi_t(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, d)\} = \max \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}} : \mathbb{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}}, d_c \right\} \tag{26c}$$

where d_c is the critical stored energy defined as

$$d_c = \frac{f_t^2}{2E} \tag{27}$$

in which, f_t is the uniaxial tensile strength and E denotes the Young's modulus.

3. Numerical implementation and solution strategy

3.1. Weak form and finite element approximation

The phase field model is commonly solved within finite element (FE) framework [24,37,68]. To begin FE approximation, the phase field model aims to find an admissible displacement field \mathbf{u} and an admissible phase field d that satisfies the minimization of the total Euler–Lagrange free energy in Eq. (16) as follows

$$\{\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}), d(\mathbf{x})\} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{S}_u, d \in \mathcal{S}_d} \Pi_\ell(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}), d) \quad (28)$$

where \mathcal{S}_u and \mathcal{S}_d are the admissible displacement field space and admissible phase field space, respectively, which are defined as

$$\mathcal{S}_u = \{\mathbf{u} | \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \text{ on } \partial\Omega_u, \mathbf{u} \in H^1(\Omega)\} \quad (29a)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_d = \{d(\mathbf{x}) | \nabla d \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega, 0 \leq d(\mathbf{x}) \leq 1, \delta d(\mathbf{x}) \geq 0\} \quad (29b)$$

In FEM framework, the discrete approximations of displacement and phase field are expressed in the following forms.

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathbf{N}_I^u \mathbf{u}_I \quad (30a)$$

$$d = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathbf{N}_I^d d_I \quad (30b)$$

where \mathbf{u}_I and d_I are the nodal vector of displacement and phase field value at I th node, respectively; n denotes the total number of nodes in an element; \mathbf{N}_I^u and \mathbf{N}_I^d are the shape functions of displacement and phase fields in the standard FEM that are defined as the following forms for 2D plane strain problems

$$\mathbf{N}^u = \begin{bmatrix} N_1 & 0 & \cdots & N_n & 0 \\ 0 & N_1 & \cdots & 0 & N_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (31a)$$

$$\mathbf{N}^d = [N_1 \quad \cdots \quad N_n] \quad (31b)$$

Similarly, the strain tensor field and the gradient of phase field in the standard FEM can be approximated as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathbf{B}_I^u \mathbf{u}_I \quad (32a)$$

$$\nabla d = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathbf{B}_I^d d_I \quad (32b)$$

where \mathbf{B}_I^u represents the derivative matrix of shape function for the displacement field, and \mathbf{B}_I^d denotes the derivative matrix of shape function for the phase field, which are expressed as follows

$$\mathbf{B}^u = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1,x} & 0 & \cdots & N_{n,x} & 0 \\ 0 & N_{1,y} & \cdots & 0 & N_{n,y} \\ N_{1,y} & N_{1,x} & \cdots & N_{n,y} & N_{n,x} \end{bmatrix} \quad (33a)$$

$$\mathbf{B}^d = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1,x} & \cdots & N_{n,x} \\ N_{1,y} & \cdots & N_{n,y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (33b)$$

The weak form of the equilibrium is formulated and its corresponding residual term for the displacement field is

$$\mathbf{R}^u = \int_{\Omega} [g(d) \mathbf{B}^{uT} (\mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_e^+ + \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_e) + \mathbf{B}^{uT} \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_e^- - \mathbf{N}^{uT} \mathbf{b}] d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega_t} \mathbf{N}^{uT} \bar{\mathbf{t}} dS \quad (34)$$

Similarly, the weak form of crack evolution equation is also derived

$$\mathbf{R}^d = \int_{\Omega} \left\{ \left[\frac{\mathcal{G}}{\ell_c} + 2\mathcal{G}_c \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) \eta \right] \mathbf{N}^d d + \mathcal{G}_c \ell_c \mathbf{B}^{dT} \nabla d - 2\mathbf{N}^d \mathcal{G}_c \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) \eta \right\} d\Omega \quad (35)$$

where \mathbb{C}_e denotes the fourth-order stiffness tensor that can be decomposed into the volumetric part $\mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}}$ and the deviatoric deformation part $\mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}}$.

$$\mathbb{C}_e = \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}} + \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}} = \lambda \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} + 2\mu \mathbb{I} \tag{36}$$

3.2. Nonlinear solution strategy

To solve the nonlinear governing equations with the boundary constraints in Eq. (28), the nonlinear optimization problems aim at finding the admissible displacement and phase fields, which fulfill the following conditions.

$$\mathbf{R}^u = \mathbf{0} \tag{37a}$$

$$R^d = 0 \tag{37b}$$

In the fully monolithic solution strategy, the trial displacement and phase fields can be computed by the following linear system of equations.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}^{uu} & \mathbf{K}^{ud} \\ \mathbf{K}^{du} & \mathbf{K}^{dd} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{u} \\ \delta d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}^u \\ R^d \end{bmatrix} \tag{38}$$

where the components of stiffness matrix are

$$\mathbf{K}_e^{uu} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^u}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \int_{\Omega_e} g(d) \mathbf{B}^{uT} (\mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}} + \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}}) \mathbf{B}^u d\Omega \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \geq 0 \tag{39a}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_e^{uu} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^u}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = \int_{\Omega_e} [g(d) \mathbf{B}^{uT} \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}} \mathbf{B}^u + \mathbf{B}^{uT} \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}} \mathbf{B}^u] d\Omega \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) < 0 \tag{39b}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_e^{ud} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^u}{\partial d} = \int_{\Omega_e} g'(d) \mathbf{B}^{uT} \left[\mathbb{C}_e^{\text{vol}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_e \left(\frac{\mathcal{G}_c - \mathcal{G}_{Ic}}{\mathcal{G}_c} \right) + \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_e \left(\frac{\mathcal{G}_c - \mathcal{G}_{IIc}}{\mathcal{G}_c} \right) \right] N^d d\Omega \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \geq 0 \tag{40a}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_e^{ud} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^u}{\partial d} = \int_{\Omega_e} g'(d) \mathbf{B}^{uT} \mathbb{C}_e^{\text{dev}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_e \left(\frac{\mathcal{G}_c - \mathcal{G}_{IIc}}{\mathcal{G}_c} \right) N^d d\Omega \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) < 0 \tag{40b}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_e^{du} = \mathbf{K}_e^{ud} \tag{41}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_e^{dd} = \frac{\partial R^d}{\partial d} = \int_{\Omega} \left[\mathcal{G}_c \ell_c \mathbf{B}^{dT} \mathbf{B}^d + \frac{\mathcal{G}_c}{\ell_c} N^d N^d + 2\mathcal{G}_c \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{\mathcal{G}_{IIc}} \right) \eta N^d N^d \right] d\Omega \tag{42}$$

The external loads are applied in a stepwise manner. For the time interval $[t, t + 1]$, the following linear system of equations reads

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}^{t+1} \mathbf{u}_I \\ {}^{t+1} d_I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^t \mathbf{K}^{uu} & {}^t \mathbf{K}^{ud} \\ {}^t \mathbf{K}^{du} & {}^t \mathbf{K}^{dd} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} {}^{t+1} \mathbf{R}_I^u \\ {}^{t+1} R_I^d \end{bmatrix} \tag{43}$$

4. Numerical validations

In the current study, all numerical simulations are carried out under the two-dimensional plane strain assumption. Moreover, the code used for numerical computations is developed using Matlab and Paraview. The simulations are executed on a PC with a AMD[®] Ryzen 9-3900X processor with 32 GB of RAM. A NVIDIA GeForce RTX[®] 2060 SUPER[™] card is employed to accelerate the computations.

In this section, two three-point bending tests, including one centrally notched and one eccentrically notched concrete beams are simulated to validate the phase field model with the new crack driving forces. The geometric and loading conditions of the two beams are depicted in Fig. 4. The material properties are: Young's modulus $E = 2.0$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$, mode-I fracture energy $\mathcal{G}_{Ic} = 5.0$ J/m², mode-II fracture energy $\mathcal{G}_{IIc} = 15\mathcal{G}_{Ic}$ and the length scale parameter $\ell_c = 1.5$ mm. For the centrally notched beam, the computational domain is discretized into 8235 quadratic elements with $h_{max} = 3.5$ mm and $h_{min} = 0.6$ mm; while, for the eccentrically notched beam, the computational domain is discretized into 11,698 triangular elements with the same maximum and minimum

Fig. 4. Geometric and boundary conditions of two notched three-point bending tests of concrete with unit of mm [72,73].

Fig. 5. Failure evolution process of a centrally notched concrete beam in the three-point bending test.

sizes. We use the two types of elements to demonstrate the robustness of our model. A constant incremental displacement of $\Delta u_y = 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mm is applied to the centers of the two beams, as shown in Fig. 4.

The development of the crack in the centrally notched beam is depicted in Fig. 5(a). The crack growth paths predicted by the modified phase field model agree well with those from literature [72,73]. The field of effective maximum principal stress is plotted in Fig. 5(b), from which we can find that the effective maximum principal stress is symmetrically concentrated around the crack tip, driving the crack initiation and propagation. Similarly, the crack growth paths and the effective maximum principal stress fields in the eccentrically notched specimens are plotted in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b), respectively. The asymmetric concentration of the stress fields around the crack tip gives rise to crack paths deviating from the notch tip. The curved crack path is in agreement with the existing results [72,73].

Fig. 6. Failure evolution process of an eccentrically notched concrete beam in the three-point bending test.

Furthermore, Figs. 7(a) and 7(b) show the comparisons of load versus crack mouth displacement curves for the two beams, respectively. It can be observed that the current numerical results are in good agreement with the experimental data [72] and Feng and Wu [73]. This finding indicates the correctness and accuracy of our new phase field model.

To evaluate the numerical convergence properties of our new phase-field model, the structured finite element meshes with four different levels of refinement are used to model the centrally and eccentrically notched concrete beams in the three-point bending tests, as shown in Fig. 8. The inherent characteristic length of concrete is fixed as $\ell_c = 1.5$ mm, while the minimum value of mesh size h_{\min} changes, which results in the variation of the nonlocal ratio ℓ_c/h_{\min} . In the numerical convergence tests, the nonlocal ratios of the new phase-field model are set as $\ell_c/h_{\min} = 1.25$, $\ell_c/h_{\min} = 1.5$, $\ell_c/h_{\min} = 1.20$ and $\ell_c/h_{\min} = 2.50$.

The ultimate crack growth paths in the centrally and eccentrically notched concrete beams are plotted in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b), respectively. It can be observed from Fig. 8 that the ultimate failure patterns are slightly affected by the variation of h_{\min} . When the inherent characteristic length ℓ_c is fixed, crack growth paths become thinner with the decrease of h_{\min} , as shown in in Fig. 8. Moreover, the corresponding load versus crack mouth displacement curves for the two beams with various meshes are plotted in Figs. 9(a) and 9(b), respectively. It can be observed from Fig. 9 that the peak load gradually reaches the experimental data [72,73] when h_{\min} decreases (i.e., ℓ_c/h_{\min} increases). The numerical results illustrate that the mesh independent characteristics and the numerical convergence of our new phase-field model.

5. Numerical results and discussions

In this section, simulations of four fissured rock-like specimens under uniaxial compression are used to demonstrate the capability of our new phase field model in capturing mixed-mode fractures.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the load versus crack mouth displacement (CMD) curves for (a) centrally notched concrete beam and (b) eccentrically notched concrete beam obtained from the present phase field simulations and the existing results [72,73].

Fig. 8. Numerical convergence studies on the ultimate failure patterns in three-point bending tests with different levels of mesh refinement.

Fig. 9. Numerical convergence studies on the load versus crack mouth displacement (CMD) curves in the three-point bending tests with different levels of mesh refinement.

Fig. 10. Geometric and loading conditions of fissured rock-like specimens with different preexisting fissures.

The geometry and boundary conditions of the four fissured rock-like specimens are shown in Fig. 10. The dimensions of the specimen are 152.4 mm in height and 76.2 mm in width. The physical properties of the rock-like material are: Young’s modulus $E = 4.2$ GPa, Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.3$, mode-I fracture energy $G_{Ic} = 5.0$ J/m² and mode-II fracture energy $G_{IIc} = 13G_{Ic}$. The four specimens are discretized into irregular triangular finite element meshes with $h_{max} = 6.0$ mm and $h_{min} = 0.5$ mm, as shown in Fig. 10. The characteristic length in phase-field model is $\ell_c = 1.2$ mm. Furthermore, a constant increment displacement of $\Delta u_y = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mm is applied on the top boundary while the bottom of the specimens is fixed.

5.1. Example-I: Rock-like specimen with a single preexisting fissure

The first specimen contains a single preexisting fissure with length of $2a = 12.7$ mm located at the center and inclined with $\alpha = 30^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 8(a). The computational domain is discretized into 40,466 triangular elements.

Fig. 11 shows the evolution of failure, including crack growth paths, the maximum principal stress fields and maximum shear stress fields at different loading steps. The loading steps in Fig. 11 correspond to the points on the axial stress–strain curve depicted in Fig. 12. As shown in Figs. 11 and 12, wing cracks are firstly initiated around the preexisting fissure tips due to the stress concentration. The wing cracks then propagate along the direction of uniaxial compressive loads, and the secondary shear cracks and anti-wing cracks nucleate around the fissure tips, simultaneously. In the post-peak loading stages (Fig. 12), driven by the concentration of maximum principal stress (Fig. 11b), the wing cracks continue to propagate towards the bottom and upper boundaries, and the anti-wing cracks propagate along the direction perpendicular to the fissure caused by the complex stress fields (Fig. 11b and c). Furthermore, the secondary shear cracks extend along the direction of the fissure driven by the maximum shear stress fields (Fig. 11c). Figs. 11 and 12 also indicate that the propagation of wing cracks transforms from stable to unstable during the failure process. On the other hand, the unstable crack growth dominates the propagation of the anti-wing and secondary shear cracks. The final topology of the cracks is in good agreement with the experimental observations reported by Lajtai [74], as shown in Fig. 13(a)–(b). This good agreement indicates that the proposed phase field model can reliably predict the propagation of tensile and shear cracks.

Moreover, to demonstrate the significant improvement in predicting mixed fracture patterns by the proposed thermodynamically consistent phase field model with new crack driving forces, the current numerical results are

(a) Phase field evolution process

(b) Maximum principal stress evolution process with unit of MPa

(c) Maximum shear stress evolution process with unit of MPa

Fig. 11. The failure process of fissured rock-like specimen containing one single preexisting crack subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads.

compared with the predicted crack growth paths by the previous phase-field simulations [57], as shown in Fig. 13(c). It is observed from Fig. 13(b)–(c) that the previous phase-field simulations [57] only succeed in simulating secondary shear cracks, but failed in predicting the wing cracks and anti-wing cracks in rock-like materials under the uniaxial compression. Fig. 13 also indicates that our new phase field model is more efficient and robust than the previous one in simulating mixed-mode fracture in rock-like materials.

Video S1 in appendix shows the evolution of crack growth paths, maximum principal stress fields and maximum shear stress fields in the first specimen.

Fig. 12. The axial stress–strain curve for the fissured rock-like specimen under the uniaxial compression obtained from the phase field simulations.

Fig. 13. Comparison of the ultimate crack growth paths in the fissured rock-like specimen subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads obtained from (a) current phase field simulations, (b) existing laboratory experiments [74] and (c) previous phase-field simulations [57].

5.2. Example-II: Rock-like specimen with two collinear preexisting fissure

The second specimen contains two collinear preexisting fissures with the same length of $2a = 12.7$ mm, rock bridge length of $2b = 20.0$ mm and fissure inclined angle of $\alpha = 30^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 8(b). The computational domain is discretized into 27,154 triangular elements.

The predicted crack initiation, propagation and coalescence under uniaxial compression are plotted in Fig. 14. The crack initiation and crack coalescence points are also depicted on the numerical axial stress–strain curve, as shown in Fig. 15. During the progressive failure process, the wing cracks first initiate at the upper and lower tips of the two fissures due to the concentration of maximum principal stress (Figs. 14(a) and 14(b)). When the uniaxial compressive loads continue to apply, the wing cracks also continue to propagate along the direction of the maximum

(a) Phase field evolution process

(b) Maximum principal stress evolution process with unit of MPa

(c) Maximum shear stress evolution process with unit of MPa

Fig. 14. The failure process of fissured rock-like specimen containing two parallel collinear preexisting cracks subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads.

principal stress. Similarly, the secondary shear cracks initiate around the fissure tips due to the concentration of shear stress, as shown in Figs. 14(a) and 14(c). As the applied loads increase, the secondary shear cracks initiate from the inner tips of two fissures, and propagate towards each other with a slight offset angle. Finally, a out-of-plane shear crack links the secondary shear cracks in the rock bridge region, which results in the mixed tensile-shear crack coalescence mode, as shown in Fig. 14(a). From Figs. 14(b) and 14(c), it can be found that the compressive shear stress fields activate the appearance of out-of-plane shear crack, which bring about the shear crack coalescence

Fig. 15. The axial stress–strain curve for the fissured rock-like specimen with two parallel collinear preexisting cracks under the uniaxial compression obtained from the phase field simulations.

Fig. 16. Comparison of ultimate crack growth paths in the fissured rock-like specimen containing two parallel collinear preexisting cracks subjected to uniaxial compressive loads obtained from (a) current phase field simulations, (b) existing laboratory experiments [75,76] and (c) previous phase-field simulations [57].

mode. Figs. 14 and 15 also indicate that the propagation of wing cracks transforms from a stable state to an unstable state, while the secondary shear cracks unstably propagate until crack coalescence and ultimate failure happen.

Furthermore, the current numerical results, the existing experimental observations [75,76] and the previous phase-field simulations [57] are compared in Fig. 16. It can be observed from Fig. 16 that the currently predicted failure patterns agree with the experimental observations [75,76], which indicates that the proposed model can successfully simulate mixed-mode fracture initiation, propagation and coalescence in rock-like materials. As shown in Fig. 16(a) and (c), when compared with the previous phase-field simulations [57], the previous numerical model is only successful in predicting shear cracks, but fails in predicting wing cracks. The above comparison demonstrates that our thermodynamically consistent phase field model with the new crack driving forces better predicts the mixed-mode fracture in rock materials. In addition, evolution of cracks and the stress fields can be also viewed in Video S2 attached with this paper.

5.3. Example-III: Rock-like specimen with two parallel preexisting fissures

The third specimen contains two parallel preexisting fissures with the same length of $2a = 12.7$ mm and the rock bridge length of $2b = 20.0$ mm. The fissure inclined angle is $\alpha = 30^\circ$ and the rock bridge angle is $\beta = 60^\circ$, as shown in Fig. 8(c). The computational domain is discretized into 30,528 triangular elements.

The evolutions of crack growth paths, maximum principal stress fields, and maximum shear stress fields are depicted in Figs. 17(a)~17(c), respectively. The typical points of different prescribed displacements are also plotted on the stress–strain curve in Fig. 18. When the applied displacement reaches $u_y = 0.03$ mm, the wing cracks initiate from the fissure tips. With the increase of vertical displacement, the wing cracks propagate along the vertical direction and the nucleation of the secondary shear cracks occurs, as shown in Fig. 17(a). The maximum shear stress fields dominate the propagation and coalescence of the secondary shear cracks in the rock bridge region, as shown in Fig. 17(c). It can also be observed from Fig. 17(a) that the wing cracks initiated from the inner fissure tips are suppressed by the shear crack coalescence. From Figs. 17(b) and 17(c), the compressive stress around the inner fissure tips and the maximum shear stress around the secondary shear crack tips both contribute to the inhibition of the inner wing cracks during the failure process. Typical points on the axial stress–strain curve in Fig. 18 indicate that the wing crack propagation changes from stable to unstable, whereas the propagation of the secondary shear cracks is unstable during the progressive failure process of the specimen with two parallel preexisting fissures under the uniaxial compression.

The ultimate crack coalescence pattern obtained from our new phase field simulations is compared with the experimental observations [77] and the previous phase-field predictions [58], as shown in Fig. 19. It can be observed from Fig. 19(a) and (b) that the current phase-field predictions well agree with the existing experimental observations. Our new model successfully predicts the pure shear crack coalescence in the rock bridge region and captures the secondary shear cracks initiated from the outer tips of preexisting fissures. However, the previous phase field model [56,58] cannot capture the secondary shear cracks due to the neglect of the mixed compressive-shear damage degradations. Again, the evolution of the cracks and associated fields can also be found in the attached Video S3.

5.4. Example-IV: Rock-like specimen with three parallel preexisting fissures

Three parallel preexisting fissures present in the fourth specimens. It can be observed from Fig. 8(d) that the preexisting fissure length is $2a = 12.7$ mm, rock bridge lengths are $2b = 2c = 20.0$ mm. The fissure inclined angle is $\alpha = 30^\circ$ and the rock bridge angle is $\beta = 60^\circ$. The computational domain discretized by 29,058 triangular elements is also depicted in Fig. 8(d).

The predicted crack growth paths and the associated maximum principal stress fields and maximum shear stress fields are plotted in Figs. 20(a)~20(c), respectively. When the applied prescribed axial displacement reaches $u_y = 0.03$ mm, the wing cracks are initiated from the fissure tips, as shown in Figs. 20(a) and 20(b). When the axial displacement reaches $u_y = 0.061$ mm, the secondary shear cracks initiate around the fissure tips due to the concentration of maximum shear stress fields, as shown in Figs. 20(a) and 20(c). As the prescribed axial displacement increases, it can be observed that the wing cracks propagate along the loading direction and the secondary cracks extend along the direction of the fissures. Meanwhile, the anti-wing cracks also initiate from the fissure tips and they propagate along the direction perpendicular to the fissures. From the analysis of stress fields, the anti-wing cracks are tension-induced, and this observation is well corroborated by results [76]. Finally, in the bridge region, the anti-wing cracks coalesce with each other and the secondary shear cracks link with the wing cracks. The mixed tensile-shear crack coalescence and pure tensile crack linkage result in the ultimate failure mode.

Each typical stress points, including the crack initiation stress points and the crack coalescence stress points are depicted on the axial stress–strain curves, as shown in Fig. 21. Figs. 20 and 21 also indicate that the wing crack propagation transforms from the stable way to unstable one, and the development of other cracks is unstable. The ultimate failure mode is in good agreement with the experimental pattern [78], as shown in Fig. 22. This agreement indicates the reliability and robustness of the model. Besides, the cracking process of fissured rock-like specimen with three parallel preexisting fissures can be found in Video S4.

(a) Phase field evolution process

(b) Maximum principal stress evolution process with unit of MPa

(c) Maximum shear stress evolution process with unit of MPa

Fig. 17. The failure process of fissured rock-like specimen containing two parallel preexisting cracks subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads.

5.5. Parametric study

To further demonstrate the capability of the proposed phase field model in predicting complex crack coalescence modes under the uniaxial compression, three fissured specimens with three parallel fissures with different another ligament angle β , i.e., $\beta = 45^\circ$, $\beta = 75^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$, are simulated. When the ligament angle is $\beta = 45^\circ$ or $\beta = 75^\circ$, mixed crack coalescence mode occurs in the rock bridge region, as shown in Figs. 23(a) and 23(b). As the ligament

Fig. 18. The axial stress–strain curve for the fissured rock-like specimen with two parallel preexisting cracks under the uniaxial compression obtained from the phase field simulations.

Fig. 19. Comparison of the ultimate crack growth paths in the fissured rock-like specimen containing two parallel preexisting cracks subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads obtained from the current phase field simulations, the existing laboratory experiments [77] and the previous phase-field simulations [58].

angle β increases to 90° , it can be observed from Fig. 23(c) that the pure tensile/shear crack coalescence modes takes place. However, no mixed tensile-shear crack coalescence mode can be found in the rock bridge region.

As the ligament angle β increases from 45° to 90° with an interval of 15° , the ultimate crack coalescence modes in the rock bridge zones transform from the mixed tensile-shear crack coalescence mode to the pure tensile/shear crack coalescence one, as shown in Figs. 22 and 23. The parametric study reveals the complex failure characteristics of the fissured specimens under uniaxial compression, which is beneficial to the stability assessment of rock slopes and underground surrounding rock masses.

Moreover, the impact of the ligament angle β on the crack coalescence stress and strain is also investigated, and the results are plotted in Fig. 24. When the ligament angle β increases from 75° , it can be observed that the crack

(a) Phase field evolution process

(b) Maximum principal stress evolution process with unit of MPa

(c) Maximum shear stress evolution process with unit of MPa

Fig. 20. The failure process of fissured rock-like specimen containing three parallel preexisting cracks with ligament angle β of 60° subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads.

coalescence stress increases, while the crack coalescence strain decreases. In contrast, when the ligament angle β continues to increase, the crack coalescence stress gradually decreases, while the crack coalescence strain increases, as shown Fig. 24. The typical values of the crack coalescence stress and strain obtained in the investigations suggest that a low ligament angle may promote the mixed tensile-shear crack coalescence modes in rock masses with parallel discontinuous structures. The present study also disclosures that a large ligament angle may facilitate the pure shear

Fig. 21. The axial stress–strain curve for the fissured rock-like specimen with three parallel preexisting cracks under the uniaxial compression obtained from the current phase field simulations.

Fig. 22. Comparison of the ultimate crack growth paths in the fissured rock-like specimen containing three preexisting cracks with ligament angle β of 60° subjected to the uniaxial compressive loads obtained from the current phase field simulations and the previous laboratory experiments [78].

crack coalescence mode and pure tensile crack coalescence mode. The transition of fracture modes in rock bridge regions demonstrates the changing mechanism of crack coalescence with the increase of ligament angles.

6. Conclusions

In this study, a thermodynamically consistent phase field model with newly formulated crack driving forces is proposed to simulate mixed-mode fractures in rock/rock-like materials. The new crack driving forces consist of volumetric dilation and deviatoric deformation that are used to distinguish between mode-I and mode-II fracture

(a) Ligament angle β of 45°

(b) Ligament angle β of 75°

(c) Ligament angle β of 90°

Fig. 23. Effect of ligament angle β on the ultimate crack coalescence patterns in the fissured rock-like specimens with three parallel preexisting cracks under the uniaxial compression.

Fig. 24. Effect of ligament angle β on axial-strain and axial-stress at the first occurrence of crack coalescence.

based on the Benzeggagh–Kenane semi-empirical failure criterion. Our new model can also capture the mixed tensile-shear and compressive-shear fracture phenomena simultaneously. The fully monolithic solving algorithm with fast numerical convergence is developed to obtain stable solutions. Several numerical examples are used to demonstrate the predictive capability and robustness of our new model in modeling the complex crack coalescence patterns. The different crack types, including wing cracks, anti-wing cracks and secondary shear cracks, and various crack coalescence modes, i.e., tensile crack coalescence, shear crack coalescence and mixed tensile/compressive-shear crack coalescence modes, predicted by our new model well agree with the previous experimental observations. Compared with numerical simulations by the existing phase field models, the present numerical results show certain advantages of capturing the complex crack growth paths. Furthermore, the parametric study on the effect of rock bridge angles also indicates its modeling capability, which thus proves to be a promising numerical tool in geomechanics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sijia Liu: Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Figures. **Yunteng Wang:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Figures, Writing – original draft, Review revision & editing, Supervision. **Chong Peng:** Original draft, Review, Revision & editing. **Wei Wu:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Review, Revision & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2022.114642>. There are four videos for the failure evolution processes of four fissured rock-like specimens under the uniaxial compression.

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